

Socio-economic factors driving consolidation of democracies in post-socialist economies

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Abstract

The main aim of the paper is to identify important socio-economic factors affecting the consolidation of democracies in post-socialist economies. The level of democratic environment is evaluated by the Electoral Democracy Index (the V-Dem Project). The influence of socio-economic factors is analyzed from the perspective of Modernization theory, which is compared with the other four theories (early developed institutions, natural resource abundance, cultural heritage, and international trade) in the empirical analysis. To achieve the aim, the paper uses time-series cross-sectional Prais-Winsten regression models with panel-corrected standard errors. The results indicate that the consolidation of democratic environment was positively affected by economic development and historical experience with democracy and negatively influenced by natural resource abundance and Islamic cultural heritage. If we evaluate the individual factors within the Modernization theory, then we can see statistically significant influence of the economic level, while the effect of education or urbanization seems to be insignificant. At the end of the empirical analysis, the ambiguous influence of middle class as transition channel of the Modernization theory on the consolidation of democratic environment was discussed.

Keywords

democracy; modernization theory; early developed institutions; natural resource abundance; post-socialist economies

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Introduction

A political regime is a set of rules that regulates government and state institutions, on the one hand, and enables the interactivity of government institutions with society, on the other. In the European area, the theme of a political regime is largely associated with democratic or authoritarian arrangement. The extension of democratic regimes has been a long-term global process since the 1970s (Greece, Portugal, Spain) and the 1980s (Latin America) through the 1990s (the European post-socialist area) up to the present (e.g., the ‘Colors Revolutions’ and the ‘Arab Spring’). In the post-socialist economies, the process led directly to the establishment of liberal democracies (the Baltic States, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Slovenia) and authoritarian regimes (Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Russia, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan). At the same time, various types of illiberal or defective democracies have been constituted in the other countries (most of the Balkan and post-soviet states). The paper focuses on the most important theories which can explain the long run democratization in the post-socialist area in the context of the third wave of democratization with emphasis on the Modernization theory.

The main aim of the paper is to identify important socio-economic factors affecting the consolidation of democracies in post-socialist economies. The literature review provides a survey of the current theoretical and empirical literature focusing on five the most relevant theories (modernization theory, early developed institutions, natural resource abundance, ethnic fractionalization, and international trade). The time-series cross-sectional Prais-Winsten regression models with panel-corrected standard errors and used proxies are described in the methodology section. The Empirical Results and Discussion section includes a panel data regression analysis, and the significant explanatory theories are discussed. The Conclusions section summarizes the major findings.

Individual theories explaining the formation and consolidation of democracies

In the following section, the Modernization theory and the other four theories are introduced: early developed institutions, natural resource abundance, cultural heritage, and international trade.

Modernization theory. The theory is based on the idea that “democracy is related to the state of economic development, since the more well-to-do a nation, the greater the chances that it will sustain democracy” (Lipset, 1959: 75). Lipset also presents four socio-economic requisites supporting democracy, wealth, industrialization, urbanization, and education.

In the empirical literature, the wealth of society is most often associated with the level of GDP per capita (e.g., Acemoglu et al, 2008, 2009; Barro, 1999; Boix and Stokes, 2003; Cervellati et al, 2014; Hadenius and Teorell, 2005; Pop-Eleches, 2007; Przeworski and Limongi, 1997). Przeworski and Limongi (1997) concluded that economic development affected the consolidation of democratic regimes, whereas democratization took place only in countries with a lower economic level (see Law, Lim, and Ismail, 2013). On the other hand, Acemoglu et al (2008, 2009) argued that the link only exists within the OLS models, whereas in the case of inclusion of fixed effects or conditional historical factors (see the following section), the relation disappears (see Cervellati et al, 2014). Focusing on the post-socialist area, there are few contributions (Alexander, 2008; Pop-Eleches, 2007) dealing with the economic development as a factor of democratization, and both authors agree that economic development has a positive impact.

The level of industrialization is the second prerequisite. The process of industrialization is a historical factor that was important during the First and Second Industrial Revolutions (in Europe) and after World War II (in the former colonies). Due to the given time period, the issue of industrialization

does not offer a sufficient explanation for the democratization processes in post-socialist countries. For this reason, this factor is not further analyzed.

The third factor, the share of the urban population, is linked to the assumption that the urban population is a major supporter of democratization processes. Which means that democracy is the result of existence of cities. The influence can be found from city-states in ancient Greece to the electoral situation in the 20th century (e.g., communist movements had strong support in less urbanized countries; Lipset, 1959: 78; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2005: 17). Empirical verification is offered by Barro (1999), Easterly (2001), Dima, Leitao, and Dima (2011), and Pop-Eleches (2007).

Education is the fourth precondition. According to Lipset (1959: 79), the development of education supports the democratic regime by increasing tolerance, promoting political pluralism, and developing democratic values in society. Glaeser, Ponzetto, and Shleifer (2007) add that education also encourages civic engagement. The positive effect of education is empirically demonstrated by Barro (1999), Glaeser, Ponzetto, and Shleifer (2007), Klomp and De Haan (2013), Murtin and Wacziarg (2014), and Papaioannou and Siourounis (2008). These authors agree that literacy has been a major factor over the last one hundred and fifty years, especially in developing countries, while secondary and higher education levels have become more important in the last fifty years (e.g., Glaeser, Ponzetto, and Shleifer, 2007; Klomp and De Haan, 2013).

Within the Modernization theory, the development of middle class is considered a transmission channel between socio-economic development and consolidation of democratic regime (Lipset, 1959: 83) because 'No bourgeois, no democracy' (Moore, 1966: 418). According to Acemoglu and Robinson (2005), the middle class balances the differences between the elites and the masses. It means the middle class tries to prevent the elite from being threatened on the one hand and strives to minimize revolutionary tendencies in the poor masses on the other hand. And the process can best be done in the democratic system. An empirical verification of these views can be found in Barro (1999) and Loayza, Rigolini, and Llorente (2012).

Early developed institutions. This theory is based on the 'critical juncture' approach according to which the current economic and political development is given by significant changes that occur differently in different countries and create a different historical heritage. Acemoglu et al (2008, 2009) stated that the correlation between economic development and democracy is given by a cross-sectional structure of data or using pooled OLS in panel data. Whereas, if fixed effects are incorporated, which means if the influence of the individual states and the time are taken into consideration, the correlation disappears (the periods 1875–2000 and 1960–2000). The authors prefer early developed institutions as an explanation, instead of the Modernization hypothesis. This means the current political and economic development trajectories are determined by historical events and institutional arrangement in the past (e.g., proxies such as settler mortality or population density in 1500 or executive constraints during the beginning of independence). Similar results can be found in Cervellati et al (2014), Faria, Montesinos-Yufa, and Morales (2014), and Jung and Sunde (2014). According to Cervellati et al (2014), the economic level has a negative impact on the development of the democratic regime in the former colonies, whereas the influence may be positive if the countries were independent in 1900 or had a democratic arrangement at the time of the modern state creation (e.g., the Baltic States, Czechoslovakia, Poland).

In the case of post-socialist economies, there are several historical factors considered by the literature to be significant, imperial power heritage (Bernhard, 1993; Bunce, 2005; Fish, 1998; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2005), interwar statehood (Pop-Eleches, 2007; Roeder, 1999), and socio-economic level in the period before the communist regime (Darden and Grzymala-Busse, 2006; Pop-Eleches, 2007).

Natural resource abundance. The resource curse might be defined as ‘the adverse effect of a country’s natural resource wealth on its economic, social, or political well-being’ (Ross, 2015: 240). According to many authors, there is a negative relationship between the abundance of natural resources and the democratic arrangement or the possibilities of democratization. The theory is based on the idea that the elites in authoritarian regimes are constantly trying to reduce or eliminate the democratic processes (e.g., Barro, 1999; Ross, 2001; 2015).

Ross (2001: 332–337) offers two explanations: the Rentier effect and the Repression effect. The first focuses on reducing the social pressures demanding the democratization. The Rentier effect can have three forms, taxation effect (income from natural wealth allows maintaining low taxation reducing efforts to gain a greater share of political power), spending effect (income from natural wealth allows buying satisfaction of population), and group formation effect (government generosity for official social groups prevents the creation of independent groups). The Repression effect means that income from natural wealth allows the creation of strong security apparatus (lower probability of a successful coup, natural resources protection against external or internal dangers).

Cultural heritage. In the paper, culture is identified with religion. According to Lipset (1994: 5), historical developments suggest that the formation of democracies is associated with Protestantism, while other religions should have a rather negative influence (Roman Catholic and Orthodox Christianity, Islam).

The different effect of individual churches can be explained by the value of religious preferences prevailing in individual countries. Grigoriadis (2016) states that authoritarian tendencies are more prevalent in collectivist religions (Roman Catholic and Orthodox Christianity, Islam), for which the presence of hierarchization is typical, while Protestantism is individualistic and is associated with a low degree of hierarchy. Another perspective is offered by Inglehart and Welzel (2010: 553–554), according to which the emphasis on self-expression and secular-rational values prevails in Protestant states leading to a more liberal approach to political and social issues in these countries. In contrast, there are Orthodox states in which preferences are focused on survival values, which leads to the support of authoritarian tendencies. At the same time, the separation of church and state is most evident in Protestant countries (Lipset, 1994: 5). In the case of post-socialist economies, Anderson (2004) and Pop-Eleches (2007) identified a positive influence of Western Christianity (Roman Catholic and Protestant Church), while Islamic cultural heritage rather created negative conditions for democratization in the countries (e.g., Fish, 1998; Pop-Eleches, 2007).

International trade. In the case of international trade, there is a general consensus that the integration into international trade has a positive impact on the formation of democratic institutions, e.g., Acemoglu and Robinson (2005), Li and Reuveny (2003), and López-Córdova and Meissner (2008). Simultaneously, López-Córdova and Meissner (2008: 575) added that positive impacts occur when there is a sufficiently high capital stock in the country, because in this case the middle class has the largest share of revenue from international trade. Acemoglu and Robinson (2005: 40–42) added that repression against democratization movements in globalized world is associated with higher costs for the given authoritarian regime. Summarization of the individual arguments can be found at Li and Reuveny (2003: 32–39).

Methodology

This section describes the individual proxies representing democratic environment and socio-economic factors and the time-series cross-sectional Prais-Winsten regression models with panel-corrected standard errors.

Dependent proxy and factors representing the Modernization theory. As indicator of the level of democratic environment, the paper uses the Electoral Democracy Index of the V-Dem Project (Coppedge et al 2020; Pemstein et al 2020). The Electoral Democracy Index (EDI) is based on the concept of Polyarchy (Dahl, 1989) and evaluates five essential parts of electoral democracy: freedom of association (*v2x_frassoc_thick*), clean elections (*v2xel_frefair*), freedom of expression (*v2x_freexp_altinf*), suffrage (*v2x_suffr*), and elected officials (*v2x_elecoff*). The V-Dem Project is preferred to the most frequent indexes of political environment (the Democracy-Dictatorship Index, the Freedom in World, and the Polity V Project) since it is more complex. Finally, let us mention that the concept of electoral democracy is linked to several research constraints (see Hadenius and Teorell, 2005; Persson and Tabellini, 2006).

The Modernization theory is, in accordance with the literature review, expressed by three proxies: GDP per capita, Share of urban population, and the Education Index. The same three indicators of the Modernization theory can be found in Pop-Eleches (2007).

GDP per capita (*log GDPpc*) is measured as real GDP per capita (constant 2010 US\$) according to the World Bank Group (2020a). The proxy is the most frequently used variable in empirical literature (e.g., Acemoglu et al, 2008, 2009; Benhabib, Corvalan, and Spiegel, 2013; Boix and Stokes, 2003; Cervellati et al, 2014; Faria, Montesinos-Yufa, and Morales, 2014; Hadenius and Teorell, 2005; Heid, Langer, and Larch, 2012; Przeworski and Limongi, 1997). The variable is expressed in logarithmic functional form.

Share of urban population (*Urban*) is expressed as share of people living in urban areas in total population (the World Bank Group, 2020f). The variable is employed in accordance with Barro (1999), Dima, Leitao and Dima (2011), and Easterly (2001).

The Education Index (*diff Edu*) is measured as arithmetic mean of Mean Years of Schooling and Expected Years of Schooling according to United Nations Development Program methodology (2020). Most of the mentioned authors (Barro, 1999; Glaeser, Ponzetto and Shleifer, 2007; Murin and Wacziarg, 2014; Papaioannou and Siourounis, 2008) used only Expected Years of Schooling, but the paper prefers more complex indicators. The proxy is expressed in the first difference due to stationarity.

Control proxies. This section describes eleven control proxies. There are lagged dependent proxy, Size of population, EBRD Transition Index, Executive Constraints at independence, Duration of communist regime, Oil rents, Trade openness, Share of Protestants, Share of Catholics, Share of Orthodox, and Share of Muslims.

The first two, lagged dependent proxy (*EDI*; Coppedge et al, 2020; Pemstein et al, 2020) and size of population (*log Pop*; the World Bank Group, 2020d), are the basic proxies, which can be found in most of empirical literature (e.g., Acemoglu et al, 2008, 2009; Benhabib, Corvalan and Spiegel, 2013; Heid, Langer and Larch, 2012). The first two proxies are general, whilst the third, the EBRD Transition Index, represents a specific phenomenon called economic transformation. The EBRD Transition Index (*EBRD*) evaluates progress in six areas of economic transformation (large-scale privatization, small-scale privatization, governance and enterprise restructuring, price liberalization, trade and foreign exchange system, and competition policy; arithmetic mean) according to the methodology of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (2016). We assume that the lagged dependent proxy and the development of transformation should have a positive effect on the dependent variable, whereas the size of the population should have a negative influence. Population size is expressed in logarithmic functional form.

The remaining eight variables represent the other four theories explaining the democratization and consolidation of democratic regimes (early developed institutions, natural resource abundance,

cultural heritage, and international trade). The selection of individual variables is based on Papaioannou and Siourounis (2008) and Pop-Eleches (2007).

Executive Constraints at independence (*ExConst*): the variable is measured as an arithmetic mean for the first five available years, if the state was independent before 1989 (zero is used for the others), and also values are normalized using the min-max normalization method. The indicator represents the theory of early developed institutions and one can suppose that experience with constitutional arrangement in the pre-communist period would have a positive influence on the establishment of liberal democracies after 1989. The proxy is used from the Polity V Project (xconst; Marshall and Gurr, 2020). The variable is selected in accordance with Acemoglu et al (2009), Cervellati et al (2014) and Papaioannou and Siourounis (2008).

Duration of the communist regime (*ComReg*): the variable is measured as the number of years under the government with the dominant role of the Communist Party. The variable represents specific conditions in the post-socialist economies and the paper supposes the longer duration of the communist regime reduces likelihood of establishing the democratic regime in the following period since the negative informal institutions (e.g., absence of ethical rules, clientelism, party patronage) deepened in the given countries (Cameron, 2007; Horváth and Zeynalov, 2014).

Oil rents (*Oil*): the variable is measured as the difference between the value of crude oil production at regional prices and total costs of production to GDP according to the World Bank Group (2020c). The proxy represents the abundance of natural resources, meaning that natural resources support authoritarian regimes (see Ross, 2001; 2015).

Share of Protestants (*diff Prot*), Share of Catholics (*diff Cath*), Share of Orthodox (*diff Orth*), and Share of Muslims (*diff Islam*): these individual variables are measured as a share of believers in the population according to the World Religion Data (Maoz and Henderson, 2013). The selected four churches represent about eighty percent of population in the post-socialist area and the inclusion of these indicators takes cultural heritage into consideration. In the case of Catholic and Protestant population, one can consider a positive influence (e.g., Barro, 1999; Boix and Stokes, 2003; Pop-Eleches, 2007) whereas in the case of Orthodox and Muslim population one can suppose a negative effect (see Barro, 1999; Grigoriadis, 2016; Papaioannou and Siourounis, 2008; Pop-Eleches, 2007). All these variables are expressed in the first difference due to stationarity.

Trade openness (*Trade*): the variable is measured as the sum of merchandise exports and imports divided by the value of GDP according to the World Bank Group (2020e). The proxy represents globalization and international trade and one can suppose a positive influence on the establishment of democratic institutions (e.g., Horváth and Zeynalov, 2014; Li and Reuveny, 2003; Papaioannou and Siourounis, 2008).

Regression model. The article focuses on twenty-seven post-communist countries (Central and Eastern Europe, the Balkans, and the post-Soviet space) during the 1990–2018 time period. For the most common method can be considered OLS regression with random or fixed effects. In our case, the model with fixed effects, because we can assume the influence of individual fixed effects. The method, however, is not applicable for two reasons. Firstly, the model contains a delayed explanatory variable, which could lead to bias estimates (see Nickell, 1981). Secondly, the method does not allow to test influence of variables representing early developed institutions, because the proxies are time invariant. There are several alternatives to the OLS method with fixed effects. If we perform basic econometric tests, these will indicate that the data contain heteroskedasticity (results of the Wald test), a first-order serial autocorrelation (the results of the Wooldridge test), and that there is a cross-sectional dependence (results of the Pesaran tests). At the same time, the panel structure contains more time

units (twenty-nine) than cross-sectional units (twenty-seven). For these reasons, I have decided to use time-series cross-sectional Prais-Winsten regression models with panel-corrected standard errors (Beck and Katz, 1995). The regression method is based on pooled OLS, so time dummy variables are added to the model (the first model) and subsequently dummy variables representing individual states are also incorporated (the second model). The procedure guarantees the robustness of results and simultaneously the influence of the individual fixed effects is considered. In accordance with empirical literature, all proxies on the right side of equations are lagged by one period. The final regression model can be expressed by the following equations:

$$EDI_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EDI_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 Modern_{i,t-1} + \sum(\beta_k Controls)_{i,t-1} + \omega_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

$$EDI_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EDI_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 Modern_{i,t-1} + \sum(\beta_k Controls)_{i,t-1} + \omega_t + \varphi_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

where i indexes the country, t denotes year. $EDI_{i,t}$ is the Electoral Democracy Index, $Modern_{i,t-1}$ is set of proxies representing the Modernization theory (GDP per capita in logarithmic functional form; the Education Index in first difference; Share of urban population) in previous period, $\sum(Controls)_{i,t-1}$ is set of control proxies (Size of population in logarithmic functional form; the EBRD Transition Index; Executive Constraints at independence; Duration of communist regime; Oil rents; Trade openness; Share of Protestants in first difference; Share of Catholics in first difference; Share of Orthodox in first difference; Share of Muslims in first difference) in previous period, ω_t captures year fixed effects, φ_i captures country fixed effects, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is an unobserved error term.

Empirical results and discussion

Firstly, the results of the regression analysis are presented (see Table 1), and their discussion is performed, and then an analysis of the influence of middle class (transition channel of the Modernization theory) on the level of the democratic environment is carried out.

If we focus on the individual factors of the Modernization theory, then we can see that the level of economic development measured as GDP per capita seems to be the only statistically significant factor, while in the case of urbanization the significance disappears after the inclusion of individual (country) fixed effects and the influence of education is statistically insignificant in both cases. Specifically, the results suggest that a one percent increase in GDP per capita leads to an increase in the Electoral Democracy Index value by 0.02 points. The significance of per capita GDP is consistent with the literature dealing with the post-socialist economies (Alexander, 2008; Pop-Eleches, 2007).

On the other hand, it should be added that the more recent literature on democratization and regime consolidation (Broderstad, 2018) argues that income mainly has an effect on the consolidation of the democratic regime (prevention of de-democratization; Fukuyama, 2005: 163), especially in the case of the third wave of democratization countries (Teorell, 2010: 142). If we put together the results of all three factors, then we cannot unequivocally say whether the Modernization theory can sufficiently explain the political changes in the post-socialist space in the last thirty years.

Out of the individual control proxies, one can suppose that level of democratic environment has been positively affected by levels of democratic environment in previous period (the basic premise of all thematic articles) and by progress in carrying out economic transformation. On the other hand, there has been a negative impact of the population size, but only in the case of non-inclusion of country fixed effects.

Additionally, there can be a significant impact of early developed institutions, positive in case of executive constraints at independence (*ExConst*) and negative in case of duration of communist regime (*ComReg*), negative influence of natural resources abundance (*Oil*), and cultural heritage with ambiguous influence (*diff Islam*). These four findings are discussed next.

Table 1. Influence of Socio-economic Factors on Level of Political Environment

Electoral Democracy Index	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
log GDP per capita (t-1)	0.017*** (5.66)	0.022*** (2.91)				
Urban population (t-1)			0.053*** (3.13)	0.078 (1.06)		
diff Education Index (t-1)					-0.003 (-0.02)	-0.029 (-0.19)
Electoral Democracy Index (t-1)	0.847*** (38.04)	0.763*** (30.86)	0.859*** (39.70)	0.770*** (32.19)	0.871*** (47.02)	0.722*** (30.94)
log Population (t-1)	-0.003** (-2.14)	-0.004 (-0.20)	-0.003* (-1.75)	-0.001 (-0.06)	-0.003* (-1.79)	-0.014 (-0.79)
EBRD Transition Index (t-1)	0.012*** (2.80)	-0.003 (-0.38)	0.014*** (3.23)	-0.005 (-0.53)	0.018*** (4.04)	-0.019** (-2.22)
ExConst	0.003 (0.96)	0.059* (1.83)	0.009* (1.89)	0.06** (2.50)	0.012*** (3.42)	0.108*** (7.72)
ComReg	-0.001*** (-3.77)	0.001 (0.13)	-0.001*** (-4.53)	0.003 (0.37)	-0.001*** (-2.85)	0.008 (1.44)
Oil rents (t-1)	-0.119*** (-5.72)	-0.097*** (-3.43)	-0.074*** (-3.03)	-0.086** (-2.09)	-0.080*** (-3.93)	-0.102** (-2.50)
Trade openness (t-1)	0.005 (0.97)	0.009 (1.34)	0.011* (1.71)	0.009 (1.39)	0.009 (1.61)	0.005 (0.77)
diff Catholic population (t-1)	0.202 (1.25)	0.187 (1.14)	0.195 (1.01)	0.199 (1.13)	0.201 (1.60)	0.198* (1.69)
diff Protestant population (t-1)	0.086 (0.62)	0.048 (0.34)	0.067 (0.48)	0.069 (0.49)	0.045 (0.26)	0.023 (0.13)
diff Orthodox population (t-1)	0.001 (0.02)	0.001 (0.03)	0.007 (0.16)	-0.0002 (-0.01)	0.015 (0.37)	0.016 (0.33)
diff Islamic population (t-1)	-0.507*** (-5.32)	-0.472*** (-4.82)	-0.524*** (-5.46)	-0.467*** (-4.76)	-0.539*** (-5.73)	-0.464*** (-4.72)
Time effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Country effects	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES
Observations	702	702	726	726	657	657
R ² adj.	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99

Source: Authors' results. Values are least square dummy variable regression coefficients with panel corrected standard errors in parentheses; Fixed effects are estimated as dummy variables (time and country effects) but are not reported in the table; Constant is not reported in the table; ExConst is executive constraints at first five years of independence before 1990; ComReg is duration of the communist regime; (.) * indicates significance level at 0.10 level, ** indicates significance level at 0.05 level, *** indicates significance level at 0.01 level.

Political development in the 19th century and in the first half of the 20th century is considered historical factor (proxy *ExConst*) since Bunce (2005) and Roeder (1999) argued that there is a link between the establishment of liberal democracy and the formation of national identity and nation building in the pre-communist area. In the case of the Central European countries, it is possible to see the historical heritage of the Habsburg monarchy, because Austria-Hungary offered a relatively liberal regime in which the national consciousness could develop (Bernhard, 1993). Moreover, the Baltic States and Central European countries were independent in the interwar period and relatively democratic at the beginning of the period. Although the regimes with strong authoritarian characteristics were gradually established in these states (Lithuania and Poland 1926, Estonia and

Latvia 1934), there was still a strong civil society with autonomy, the press was relatively free, and the political parties had a considerable influence in the parliament, which has positively manifested in the development of civil society after 1989 (Bernhard, 1993: 310–311).

Bernhard (1993: 310–311) and Crawford and Lijphart (1997: 11) described the negative influence of the communist past on the formation of democratic regimes (proxy *ComReg*). According to these authors, the unsuccessful democratic development of the Balkan and post-Soviet republics is due to the Communist historical heritage, which may include various areas, economic (inefficient economic system resulting from the centrally planned economy), institutional (persistence of informal institutions from the previous regime), national (interruption of the nation-building process), political (standard political parties did not develop), and social (insufficient succession elite during the transformation). Let us also mention that all these factors influenced the political development of Belarus in the first half of the 1990s.

The Oil rents (Oil) as representant of natural resources abundance has expected negative impact on level of political environment (e.g., Almaz, 2015; Franke, Gawrich, and Alakbarov, 2009; Shaw, 2013). The negative effect has been most evident in the Central Asian republics and Azerbaijan since income from natural wealth reduces the need for institutional reform. Specifically, Almaz (2015) and Shaw (2013) described the negative effect in the case of Azerbaijan while Franke, Gawrich, and Alakbarov (2009) explained the curse of abundance using the example of Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan. According to Franke, Gawrich, and Alakbarov (2009), during the collapse of the Soviet Union, the original nomenclature elite remained in power by controlling oil resources and subsequently transformed the political regime into a patrimonial structure associated with corruption and rent seeking. The process of establishing authoritarian regime was also facilitated by the fact that these countries chose a political system of the presidential type and political opposition was weak. Moreover, oil wealth has enabled them to gain international legitimacy through the inflow of foreign capital (see Bayulgen, 2005).

Our results suggest a negative effect of Islamic cultural heritage, which is an opinion that prevails in the thematic literature (e.g., Barro, 1999), especially in the case of the Central Asian republics (e.g., Fish, 1998: 205; Pop-Eleches: 914). Anderson (2004: 205) added that the Islamic cultural heritage has limited the possibilities of democratization rather than supported authoritarian regimes. Compared to other authors we have not identified the influence of Protestantism (Norkus, 2007) and Western Christianity (Anderson, 2004: 205; Pop-Eleches, 2007: 914).

With respect to the influence of Modernization theory's individual factors via the middle class in the post-socialist space, the results are graphically shown in Figure 1. One can see a positive relationship between strong middle class and democratic development in the case of the Czech Republic and Slovenia (e.g., Tridico, 2013). On the other hand, Russia exhibits a weak middle class combined with a de-democratization process (e.g., McFaul, Petrov, and Ryabov: 284). Nevertheless, most of the surveyed countries are outside the confidence interval, which means that the link between the middle class and democratization is not very strong. In the case of democratic states such as Croatia and Slovakia, the development of the middle class along with market reforms has led to the consolidation of the democratic regime (e.g., Corricelli, 2007). In authoritarian states, however, where middle-class status was strongly linked to the state sector (e.g., Belarus), the result was that middle class was generally unsupportive of democracy (Rosenfeld, 2021: 437). To conclude the section, we should mention Ekiert (2010: 119) who argued that the fall of communism was the last successful middle-class revolution, subsequent developments in post-socialist economies showing that the middle class is a cultural and historical phenomenon weakened politically by postmodernity.

Figure 1. Middle class and change in level of political environment.

Note: The X-axis shows the average size of middle class in the years 1990–2017 (income share held by the second to fourth quintiles according to the World Bank Group, 2020b); the Y-axis measures the change in the level of political environment (difference between the average values for the first and last five analyzed years; the Electoral Democracy Index; Coppedge et al, 2020; Pemstein et al, 2020); the gray zone represents 95% confidence interval; Source: author's own calculations.

Conclusions

The main aim of the paper was to identify important socio-economic factors affecting the consolidation of democracies in post-socialist economies. The level of democratic environment is evaluated by the Electoral Democracy Index (the V-Dem Project). The aim was achieved using time-series cross-sectional Prais-Winsten regression models with panel-corrected standard errors, in which five explanatory theories were tested (modernization theory, early developed institutions, natural resource abundance, cultural heritage, and international trade). In accordance with the empirical literature (e.g., Papaioannou and Siourounis, 2008), the selected theories were tested against modernization theory, which was considered to be the main explanatory socio-economic factor. The approach ensures the robustness of empirical results.

Based on the results of the regression analysis, it can be argued that the level of economic development measured as GDP per capita seems to be the only statistically significant factor, while in the case of urbanization the significance disappears after the inclusion of country fixed effects and the influence of education is statistically insignificant in both cases. Specifically, the results suggest that a one percent increase in GDP per capita leads to an increase in the Electoral Democracy Index value by 0.02 points. This leads us to the conclusion that a higher economic level creates the conditions for the consolidation of a democratic regime, or rather prevents de-democratization (Broderstad, 2018;

Teorell, 2010: 142). If we put together the results of all three factors, then we cannot unequivocally say whether the Modernization theory can sufficiently explain the political changes in the post-socialist space in the last thirty years. Which can be explained by the fact that the middle class had limited impact on consolidation of the political environment, especially in the case of the post-Soviet area.

Early developed institutions in the period before the formation of the Eastern Bloc had a significant influence on the establishment and consolidation of liberal democracies (Central Europe and the Baltics) and one authoritarian regime (Belarus) after 1989. The conclusions are in accordance with other empirical contributions dealing with both developed and developing economies (Acemoglu et al, 2008, 2009; Cervellati et al, 2014) and the post-socialist countries (Darden and Grzymala-Busse, 2006; Pop-Eleches, 2007). On the other hand, there are the Central Asian Republics and Azerbaijan, where the influence of the abundance of natural resources was manifested in the formation and consolidation of authoritarian regimes. Cultural heritage may be considered another important factor, but it should also be mentioned that the influence of individual religious churches is ambiguous. with one exception, the negative impact of Islamic cultural heritage (Fish, 1998; Pop-Eleches, 2007).

As a possible extension, the paper proposes three possibilities. Firstly, the results could be extended by other econometric techniques (e.g., employing of instrumental variables or taking regional differences into consideration). Secondly, the level of democratic environment is identified only with the concept of Polyarchy (see V-Dem Project methodology), thus other attributes of political arrangement (e.g., liberal, deliberative, egalitarian, or participatory principles) or the importance of individual political regimes (liberal and electoral democracies, electoral and closed autocracies; democracy, anocracy and autocracy) are not considered. Thirdly, the paper only deals with development of political environment in post-socialist area, so it might be interesting to compare the results with changes in political regimes in the other regions (e.g., Arab Spring).

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